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The Debate about the Peaceful Rise of China

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ABSTRACT

When Chairman Hu Jintao stepped down as state president in March 2013, China's position in the world had been changed after his ten years in office. Above all, Chinese membership of the World Trade Organization (WTO) from December 2001 had stroked up a milestone of incredible development that exceeded all expectations, inside as well as outside the country. As matter of fact, what happens today in China has an enormous impact on other countries.

This paper focus on the discussion weather China raised peacefully or not.

Keywords

China, Economic growth, Peacefull rise.

Introduction

This paper has the aim to discuss weather China raised peacefully or not. The core argument of this article is that China is offering the world a better approach of negotiation, since it doesn't seek for world hegemony and has a peaceful approach when dealing with international relations.

Since the reform policy and opening to the outside, gaige kaifang, adopted by Deng Xiaoping in 1978, China began a process of rapid economic growth, as can be seen on the growth of the gross domestic product. During the first half of the 90s, the economy grew at a rapid rate over ten percent, and even despite the slowdown observed in the second half of this decade, its percentage growth has not dropped below seven percent.

China is the world's fourth major economy as well as the world's fourth largest market and the largest foreign direct investment receiver. These factors are interrelated, since one of the main reasons for China's rapid economic growth is exactly the high foreign investment, combined with the cheap and abundant labor, growing industrialization and high savings rates. Simultaneously, the Chinese government is also encouraging the internationalization of Chinese enterprises, through its policy 'go global' (zou chuqu). This strategy is already reaping its fruits, because, according to the data from the Chinese Ministry of Commerce, in 2005 the investment of Chinese entrepreneurs abroad increased 26 percent in relation to the previous year, totalizing 6,9 thousand millions American dollars. This value, however, is reduced if compared with the investment that China receives from abroad, more than 60 thousand millions dollars per year.¹

The Chinese government is promoting the industrialization of China to become a manufacturing base, gathering imported goods mainly from the Asian region and selling them to developed countries. At the same time that produces goods relatively cheap and labor-intensive, also possess a reasonable production of advanced technological goods.

However, China still remains a developing country. Beijing has adopted a strategy of three steps to achieve modernization: build a society modestly accommodated by 2020, reach an average stage of development in 2049 and, from that year, try to reach the level of a developed country. However, in order to accomplish these objectives the Chinese government still needs to solve some problems. To meet the needs of industrialization, China is becoming a major consumer of raw materials, especially energy resources. For example, since 1993, China became an importer of petroleum and ten years later, became the world's second largest importer of this resource, just after the US and ahead of Japan. It is also the largest consumer of cement and a major consumer of natural gas. On the other hand, China faces serious regional imbalances, to the extent that the economic growth is concentrated in coastal areas and cities. It will also have to tackle structural problems such as unemployment and environmental degradation, for instance.

China's entry in the World Trade Organization in 2001 was a significant step for the Chinese economy and represented not only the creation of a multitude of opportunities for its market but also the need for an increasing adequacy the international trade rules.

Will the rise of China be peaceful? The past heritage

The concept of 'peaceful rise' is closely linked to the culture and history of China. The idiosyncrasy of the Chinese people is connected to Confucian ethics and a certain idea of peacefulness in the relationship between individuals, which should be reproduced at the state level. The humanism defended by Confucius as

¹China: Foreign investments up 26 percent, *Associated Press*, July 2016.

the ideal of life in society advocates a proactive behavior, to do with others what we would like to be done with ourselves, privileging the harmony in the difference (he er bu tong).

In the Confucianism, peace is for the Chinese people one of the most important values (he wei gui).² This idea of peace and harmony was also present in the philosophies of Laozi and Mozi, the first recommending harmony with nature in a holistic conception of the cosmos, the second defending the ideal of universal love (Jianxiang'ai), at a time when different kingdoms fought violently to conquer the rest. In addition to these philosophies more connected to society, emerged also in this intellectually fertile period of the 'Hundred Schools of Thought', important strategies to gain and maintain power over the population. This is the case of the great Chinese military strategist Sunzi that curiously defended as the best strategy to know very well the enemy to subdue him without using force.³

As part of the cultural tradition of China, the idea of peace and harmony continues to mark the contemporary Chinese strategic culture, manifesting itself in the formulation of foreign policy. Although some Chinese rulers had throughout its history more violent behaviors, such as fighting against attacks of nomadic people from the North, the peaceful relations with the exterior prevails, as evidenced by the system of tributary kingdoms, developed contacts through the Silk Road and Admiral Zheng He's voyages.

After the reunification of the Seven Kingdoms under the leadership of Qin Shihuangdi, the brief Qin Dynasty (221-206 a. C.) gave place to the prosperous Han dynasty (206 a.C -220 d. C.). In this period, China has achieved a high level of development and established peaceful relations with neighboring kingdoms through the 'system of tributary kingdoms' (chaogong tizhi). Under that system, the neighboring kingdoms recognized China as a superior civilization and consequently offered a tribute. In contrast, obtained protection, and China didn't have to put into question its independence. Through this peaceful system, China has established and maintained good relations with neighboring kingdoms. This system is related to the traditional notion of harmony under heaven (tian xia), the main purpose of the Chinese emperor, the representative of Heaven on Earth. Also during the Han dynasty, it was discovered the route or routes of silk. At this period, the commercial contacts between China and the peoples of Central Asia was promoted as a way to develop a peaceful relationship, eventually the early days of commercial diplomacy in China. In addition to this economic activity, there were held cultural exchanges, which were particularly fruitful during the Tang Dynasty (618-907) and that contributed to mutual understanding and mistrust reduction. The commercial diplomacy was complemented by diplomatic boons, in which the Chinese emperors made generous offers to the rulers of Central Asia in order to promote a peaceful relationship and get allies. Although already very successful, China favored a peaceful relationship with other people.

²*The Confucian Analects*, chapters I – 12, Changsha: Hunan Press, 1992, p. 69.

³SUN ZI – *The Art of War*, capítulo 3 – «Attacking by Stratagem», Pequim: People's China Publishing House, 1995, p. 29.

This peaceful purpose was also present in the seven sea voyages of Admiral Zheng He, during the Ming Dynasty (1368-1644). Through these travels, carried out between 1405 and 1433, China established diplomatic relations, as well as commercial and cultural ties with many people of Asia and Africa. China has achieved great prestige, promoting peaceful relations with many countries through a policy in which the tax was again used as a diplomatic instrument. However, as already mentioned, China adopted violent behavior, especially with the nomadic people of the North. These attitudes were justified as a defense in a defensive realism perspective that remains today. Furthermore, China used force to extend the borders to territories over which judged to have rights or to submit rebel sovereigns, perspective that remains today. In consequence of the occupation that were targeted some of its territories, especially during the nineteenth century, the Chinese government has become very conscious of their sovereignty and territorial integrity, not allowing any separatist intent or intervention of foreign governments.

Depending on the importance of the territory in question, the Chinese government demonstrates willingness to preserve it by all means, including the use of force, the sovereignty over what it considers to be its territory. Since the implementation of the Popular Republic of China in 1949, the conflicts in which Beijing was involved were motivated by direct or indirect threats to its territory. However, this is an exception. The dominant feature of its foreign policy is the peacefulness. While Mao Zedong argued that China should never seek hegemony, Chou En-lai suggested the peaceful coexistence as a guide for the relationship with the outside, through the five principles: respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, mutual non-aggression, non-interference in internal affairs, equality and mutual benefit, and peaceful coexistence.

The current chinese politics

Recently the debate that is posed is about whether China will emerge peacefully or not. Featuring high levels of economic growth, some analysts suggest that Beijing can use these resources to modernize militarily, posing a threat to other countries. In fact, military spending has been increasing over the years. Recently, the Chinese authorities issued the national military budget ,35 100 million US dollars.⁴

According to certain estimates, the true value of military spending is two to three times higher than advertised, since it does not include spending on defense research, armament acquisition, military construction and spending on the Armed Popular Police. However, the budget remains very low compared with the military spending of other major powers. According to the report from the International Institute of Investigation on Peace of Stockholm (SIPRI), on armaments, disarmament and international security, the military spending of China reached 35400 million US dollars in 2004 (21 830 million american dollars according to the Chinese authorities), which puts it in fifth place in the sundial ranking.⁵ Much more ahead is the United States, with

⁴LI Fangchao e JIAO Xiaoyang ,Defense budget set to 14,7% rise, *China Daily*, March 6th, 2006.

⁵Apud CHEN Xulong. Truth about Military Spending, *Pequim Review*, vol. 48, n.o 27, Julho de 2005, pp. 10-13.

455300 million dollars, and Japan with 42 400 million dollars, the largest military budget in Asia and fourth in the world ranking.

Another aspect that has raised doubts about the peaceful intentions of China is its political system and a strong nationalist sentiment. Western leaders, especially the United States, have pressured the Chinese government to democratize and liberalize the political system. However, it is difficult to adopt a western type democratic system, mainly because this model is not part of Chinese political culture.

The size of the territory and the demographic weight of China are other factors that rises some suspicion by other countries, especially the neighbors since there is the fear of an unstable China. On the other hand, the Chinese communities in Southeast Asia are numerous, are controlling important sectors of the local economy and are closely linked to China. This situation has generated some suspicion by governments and even the local population in these countries.

Another aspect that has caused some concern by the countries in the region is related to conflicts in the South China Sea, specially in the Spratly archipelago. The "theory of China threat" (zhongguo weixie lun)⁶, was raised, particularly among Asian countries considered most directly threatened by the main regional power. To respond to this theory and mitigate the mistrust, the Chinese leaders reaffirmed their peaceful intentions and are increasing even more the bilateral dialogues, joint cooperation and development.

Actually, to achieve economic development, its main objective, China needs a peaceful international environment. In 1985 Deng Xiaoping announced two principles: peace and development (heping yu fazhan).⁷ Only in a peaceful environment China might develop economically. Chinese leaders know that the external and internal events are interrelated. Similar to what happened in the past, foreign aggression is linked to internal disturbances. In a situation of internal instability, outside threats can occur, while the external instability may lead to internal chaos. Both situations should be avoided. In this sense, especially since Tiananmen, when the internal disorders led to unwanted reactions from foreign governments, China's leaders have sought to demonstrate their peaceful intentions. While the 'third generation' of leaders enunciated the "new security concept", the "fourth generation" adopted the idea of peaceful rise of China.

The explicit reference to a new security concept appeared for the first time, in the "Sino-Russian declaration on a multipolar world and the establishment of a new international order" of 1997. However, only two years later, the Chinese President, Jiang Zemin, explained its contents, which included four elements: mutual trust, mutual benefit, equality and cooperation. In 2002, the content of the components of the new

⁶Perceptions of Danger: the China threat theory, *Journal of Contemporary China*, 2003, n.o 12, pp. 265-284).

⁷DENG Xiaoping .Peace and development are the two outstanding issues in the world today. In *Selected Works of Deng Xiaoping*, Vol. III (1982-1992).

security concept was presented to Southeast Asian countries, at a meeting of ASEAN, the last element was replaced by coordination, but it doesn't constitute a significant change to its content.

The mutual trust means that all countries should overcome their differences in ideology and social system, abandon the Cold War mentality and power politics and refrain from mutual suspicion and hostility. They should maintain a regular dialogue and exchange reports on their security and defense policies and major military operations.

Mutual benefit means that all countries should fulfill the objective requirements of social development in this era of globalization, respect the security interests of each and create conditions for the safety of others, while ensuring their own security interests in order to achieve common security.

Equality means that all countries, big or small, are equal members of the international community and should respect each other, treat each other as equals, refrain from interfering in the internal affairs of each other and promote the democratization of international relations.

Coordination means that all countries should seek peaceful settlement of their disputes through negotiation and promote a broad and deep cooperation on security issues of common interest, in order to eliminate potential dangers and prevent the outbreak of wars and conflicts.⁸

Finally, this "new concept" is not very innovative, since its components are almost identical to the five principles of peaceful coexistence. Its main novelty is that the Chinese leaders were more assertive in presenting a model of relationship between the states. The main features of this concept are the comprehensive security and cooperative security. Safety is taken holistically, including not only traditional military components, but also the economic aspects, cultural, social and environmental, for instance. In addition, the cooperative nature of security is strengthened and there should be coordination between the actions of states to address issues of common interest. These features demonstrate a peaceful and harmonious nature that Chinese leaders intend to assign to its foreign policy.

Following this concept, the next generation of leaders, the fourth, according to the qualification usually adopted by analysts on China, had to devise a new idea to project an international image of responsible power that should not be feared by other countries.

Since its rise to power, President Hu Jintao and the Prime Minister Wen Jiabao always defended their peaceful purposes in meetings with international leaders. In 2003, there were discussions in the Communist Party of China about the concept or the international strategy to be adopted. It was when the concept of

⁸ China's Position Paper on the New Security Concept, Geneva, 6 de August, 2002. In <www.nti.org>

"peaceful rise of China" (zhongguo heping jueqi)⁹ appeared, stressing that China should adopt peaceful means while developing. This concept was created by the vice-president of the Chinese Communist Party School, Zheng Bijian, and presented at the Boao Forum 2003.¹⁰

This concept was adopted by the Chinese leaders and included in the official speeches, namely the Prime Minister and the President. In December, both the Prime Minister Wen Jiabao and President Hu Jintao made reference to the 'peaceful rise', the first in his speech at Harvard University and the second in the discourse of commemoration of the 110 anniversary of the birth of Mao Zedong. After describing China as a peaceful civilization throughout the ages, Wen Jiabao stressed that China is a big country in development. It was not appropriate or possible, to depend on foreign countries to develop China. Thus, Chinese people must and can rely on its own efforts. In other words, while China opens further to the outside, it must fully and more consciously depend on its own structural innovations, constantly expanding the domestic market, converting the huge savings of citizens in investment, and improve the quality and progress scientific and technological to solve the problems of resources and environment. Therein lies the essence of Chinese way of peaceful rise and development.¹¹

The two main characteristics associated with the rise of China should be peace and independence. Contrasting to other countries throughout history, Chinese leaders advocate a peaceful rise model. China does not seek hegemony, like the United States neither a violent rise, such as Germany or Japan in the past. On the other hand, theoretically, the rise will be made through its own efforts, without posing harm to other countries. The prime-minister explained the five aspects associated with the peaceful rise: China should enjoy the world peace and develop; It will do it by its own effort based on their own strength but also maintaining a policy of openness and developing economic and trade exchanges with all friendly countries; this rise will require a long period of time and hard work of the people; and finally, the rise will represent no obstacle or threat to other countries.¹²

China argues that their growth benefits the neighboring countries and the world in general, an idea of common prosperity, a non-zero-sum game. Indeed, China's growth and even the decision of not devalue the yuan during the Asian financial crisis of 1997-1998, has represented new opportunities for Asian countries. Although some countries feel threatened, the truth is that China's growth stimulates the growth of other Asian economies, notably the Japanese.

⁹PENG Peng (ed.) ,Peaceful Rising Theory – The Path of China becoming a Great Power, Guangzhou: Guangdong People's Press, 2004

¹⁰ZHENG Bijian – «New path of China's peaceful rise and the Future of Asia».

¹¹Full text of Premier Wen's speech at Harvard, 12 December, 2003.

¹²Full text of Chinese Premier's press conference», 15 March, 2004.

The idea of "peaceful rise of China" was created to limit the concerns of Asian leaders on China as an economic competitor. When transmitting a peaceful attitude towards those countries, China hopes their reciprocal behavior and eventually support against the US presence in Asia, or against a possible US opposition to China. Through this strategy, embodied in partnerships and bilateral and multilateral agreements, China is creating a 'buffer zone' around its borders to protect itself from the United States.

From mid-2004, the term "peaceful rise of China" began to be less used eventually disappear from official speeches. This change was encouraged by Jiang Zemin, who remained chairman of the Central Military Commission until September of 2004. In defending the primacy of the army to ensure a prosperous nation, Jiang believed that the term "peaceful rise" would not be completely correct. One should not deny the possibility of a violent outcome in certain crises, particularly in the case of the Taiwan issue. If the leaders of the island demonstrate independence intentions, Beijing admits use force to recuperate it. The faction of Jiang Zemin has two other use of force options: against Japan and against the United States, the first because of its attitude to the past with China and the last in a possible intervention on the Taiwan issue.

On the other hand, some Chinese authors consider the word 'rise' inexact because in their view, it does not correspond to reality. Some scholars argue that China still has to solve many problems to be considered as an emerging power or a power in the ascension process. Other authors consider this term as a negative designation because it is associated with the idea of supremacy and hegemony, which the Chinese leaders have always repulsed. Consequently, Chinese leaders began to adopt new expressions such as 'peaceful revival' (heping fuxing) 'Peaceful rejuvenation' (heping Zhenxing) and especially "peaceful development" (heping Fazhan).¹³

The implications of the Chinese peaceful emergence

The reason why China has adopted this strategy has to do with the fact that it believes that to develop it needs a regional and even global peaceful environment. If it reaches its aim, its development will boost regional growth, which in turn will drive global growth, thus maintaining a peaceful international environment.

The Chinese model includes three aspects: the rise of peace, the rise for peace rise and the rise to peace.¹⁴ It means that the peaceful environment of Asia contributed to the rise of China and now China is promoting its development, both internally and externally in a peaceful way, as well as development in the region and the world.

¹³ In December of 2005, it published a White Paper on the Pacific Development Via of China.

¹⁴ WANG Yiwei, 'The dimensions of China's Peaceful Rise'. In *Asia Times*, 14 de Maio de 2004.

However, as Frank Ching states, "Beijing should take into account that the world will not only be paying attention to its words, but also to its actions'¹⁵ and what has been the behavior of China? In general, the Chinese government is using a more comprehensive strategy to forward the message of peaceful development. Chinese leaders realized that soft power is more important, so it is using it in all kinds of countries: developed, neighbors and the Third World.

The biggest partner of the emerging power is the United States but China does not want to be dependent on the superpower, by using diplomacy to approach other developed countries, such as the European Union (EU). Since 2004, with the enlargement, the EU to 25 is already its largest trading partner. According to the independent nature of its foreign policy, the Chinese government seeks to diversify as much as possible its external relationships. In recent decades, China has sought to promote relations with neighboring countries and at the same time with the countries of the Third World. China seeks to diversify the markets for which drains its products, as well as the sources of funds it needs to grow.

In practice, China is increasingly involved in international affairs, not only regional but also global. Develops good relations with the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), namely by signing the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation, the Code of Good Conduct, the Free Trade Area Agreement, and granting aid to seaquake victims in Asia. China is also one of the biggest advocates of the East Asian cooperation framework, including ASEAN countries, China, Korea and Japan. China improved relations with two of its most important neighbors, India and Russia. In Northeast Asia, China has developed efforts to resolve the issue of North Korean nuclear weapons. In the global level, has shown a more active approach in the United Nations level, participating in peacekeeping operations. As China integrates more in the international system and participate in its institutions, must take on more responsibilities and obligations. The more integrated it feels, the hypothesis about China taking violent behavior will be decreased.

Is this strategy working? According to a survey carried out, about 17 thousand people in sixteen countries in 2005, thinks that the international image of China is more favorable than the US, although the growing economic power and military raise a lot of attention, especially in Europe and Asia.¹⁶ However, a question can be raised: if China seeks a peaceful way, why does it needs a strong army?

Western leaders are usually very critical about China's military spending and raise great suspicions about the so-called peaceful intentions of Beijing.¹⁷ John Mearsheimer, from the University of Chicago, has doubts about whether China can emerge peacefully, predicting that the United States and China will probably

¹⁵CHING, Frank – «Actions speak louder than words». In *South China Morning Post*, 25 de Fevereiro de 2004.

¹⁶China "is more popular" than US. In *BBC online*, 23 June, 2005.

¹⁷ See as an example MOSHER, Steven W. – *Hegemon: China's Plan to Dominate Asia and the World*. São Francisco: Encounter Books, 2000.

get involved in an intense security competition with considerable likelihood of conflict.¹⁸ The secretary of the US Defense Donald Rumsfeld went further and stated that the military spending in Beijing threatened not only Taiwan and the United States, but also the delicate security balance in Asia.¹⁹

Despite the collaboration of Sino-American fight against terrorism, the United States continues to have serious concerns regarding China, pressing it on issues such as the political system, human rights, or even the economic system. In fact, these criticisms mask an intention to slow or stop the growth of China, avoiding that it becomes a US strategic competitor in the economic and defense field. In contrast, the United States continues to sell arms to Taiwan through the Taiwan Relations Act of 1979 to counterbalance the weight of China. However, too much pressure may turn China ``dangerous``. According to Henry Kissinger, this containment strategy will not work because ``the challenge that China presents in the medium-term future will be, most likely, political and economic, not military.²⁰

Finally, China's leaders justify their defense spending with the expression Fuguo qiangbing, that is, "prosperous nation, strong army". China is developing its economy, while strengthening its army. One of its objectives is to prepare against any attack that may possibly destabilize the economy. At the 15th of study session in July 2004, it was adopted a strategy of 'prepare for war, speaking of peace`. The preparation for war may postpone or even avoid war. The threat to use force can be a more effective deterrent measure than the actual use of force. This has to do with the strategy set out by Sunzi: the one, who is skilled in the art of war, subjugates the enemy without fighting.²¹ According to Chinese leaders, the modernization of the army does not mean that it is preparing the conflict. The military forces are necessary to achieve the political objectives and, despite certain exceptions, that's what makes all countries.

China will use force only in case of direct threat to their inalienable national interests, as the attempt of independence of Taiwan, or a threat to its sovereignty over the islands of the South Sea. It is a matter of principle that China wants to avoid losing at any cost. Indeed, the strategy of "preparing for war, speaking of peace" was adopted at the same time that Jiang Zemin criticized the idea of 'peaceful rise', safeguarding the possibility of violent behavior in specific cases. Chinese leaders argue that China is a peaceful country but will not think twice, for example, if the Taiwan leaders take the path of independence. Eventually, if the United States engages in this matter, there is a possibility of conflict between the two countries.

¹⁸MEARSHEIMER, John J. – «Better to be Godzilla than Bambi». In *Foreign Policy Special Report*, Janeiro-Fevereiro de 2005, p. 47.

¹⁹SHANKER, Thom ,Rumsfeld issues a sharp rebuke to China on arms. In *The New York Times*, 4 June, 2005.

²⁰KISSINGER, Henry .China: containment won't work. In *The Washington Post*, 13 June, 2005.

²¹SUN ZI – *The Art of War*, chapter 3 – Attacking by Stratagem, Pequim: People's China Publishing House, 1995, p. 29.

Chinese leaders have adopted a defensive realism, which means that it invests in defense to avoid losses and not to conquer, as do the offensive realists. The intention of the Chinese Government is not to intimidate its Asian neighbors, but only to send a warning to Taiwan. Furthermore, Taiwan is considered as a domestic subject, not international, nevertheless, it is an internationally relevant subject. It was precisely in this sense that, in March of 2005, a law was approved in order to avoid Taiwanese leaders to take some independent action. Despite criticism that this law was a target, it is much more passive than the previous attitude of the Chinese Government to seek reunification of the motherland. Currently, Beijing only tends to avoid pro-independence activities, including a referendum or a constitutional revision. The Chinese Government maintains that, later or sooner, will recover the government on the island, either by economic means or not. Finally, Taiwan is a matter of principle and China will not tolerate that its territory be came separated, especially after the humiliating history of foreign invasion, as known in the annals of the history of China, the last period of imperial decline.

Conclusion

Analyzing the past behavior of China, particularly with regard to external relations, we can draw some prospective lessons. In the future, China will be a power with a behavior most often peaceful, but will not hesitate to use force to defend its interests, especially those relating to sovereignty.

It seems that China will never be a superpower in the full sense of the term, that is, at all levels. It can turn into a major economic power and even military, but not a major political or cultural power. The Chinese economy is growing at a very fast pace. Currently, its size corresponds to half of the US economy and if it continues to grow each year to six percent, while the United States grows two percent, it could reach parity in 2025, becoming a major economic power. However, at the political level, the Chinese system is very specific, it is not expected that it can serve as a model for other countries. China will not be able to influence political and culturally other countries, with the exception of some Asian countries, whose conception of the world is close to the Chinese. Perhaps China will become the largest regional power, but globally its influence will be limited.

In general, China's behavior will be peaceful. China needs a peaceful international environment to grow and to develop. Chinese leaders have realized, with Tiananmen that the consequences of an internationally reprehensible attitude can be negative for its economy. China must avoid repeating these situations at all cost. On the one hand, the Chinese government shows no violent intentions, and secondly, the international society would not accept such behavior neither hegemonic aspirations. It will be very difficult for any country to take a prominent place among the great international powers, especially because they would have the US opposition. On the other hand, the other major powers together, would not allow. In fact, the

Chinese economic power demonstrated in recent years has been the target of a certain sinofobia in some European countries and the United States, which is not desirable for Beijing.

Supporter of a defensive realism, China could eventually have more violent behavior on issues that jeopardize its sovereignty and territorial integrity, but only if it is not possible to ensure it by other means. It will be the typical case of Taiwan.

Bibliography

BIJIAN, Zheng, *China's Peaceful Development and Building and Building a Harmonious World* (Beijing: People's Publishing House, 2012).

KIM Samuel, *China and the World: New Directions in Chinese Foreign Relations* (United States: Westview Press, 1989).

KORNBERG Judith and FAUST John, *China in World Politics: Policies, Processes, Prospects*, (Canada: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2005).

NYE, Joseph S. – «China's 'Peaceful' Rise?». In *China's Peaceful Rise, Les Cahiers du débat*, Maio de 2005

PENG Peng (ed.) – *Peaceful Rising Theory – The Path of China becoming a Great Power*, Guangzhou: Guangdong People's Press, 2004, p. 3.

QINGMIN, Zhang, *China's Diplomacy* (Beijing: China Intercontinental Press, 2010).

WEI WANG, Sheng. *China's Ascendancy: Opportunity or Treat?* (Washington: Library of Congress, International Publishing House for China's Culture, 2007).

YIHUANG, Zhou, *China's Diplomacy* (Beijing: China Intercontinental Press, 2004).

ZHU, Zhiqun, *China's New Diplomacy : Rationale, Strategies and Significance* (USA: Ashgate, 2013).

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